
Farm machinery

Effect of soil moisture content on tractor wheel slip

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At Pulung Kencana Village, North Lampung, the soil is clayey, red yellow Podzolic. It is very hard when dry but very sticky when wet. The area is flat and covered by cogon grass *Imperata cylindrica*. The cogon grass was cut and burned before the experiment started.

We studied the interaction of soil moisture and plowing depth in a split-plot design with four replications. Treatments were 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30% soil moisture and 10-, 15-, and 20-cm plowing depth. Plowing width was 20 cm and tractor speed during plowing was 5.4 km/h (1.5 m/s).

Equipment used was a 4-wheel 45 hp tractor IH354, a stopwatch, a soil moisture meter, and a measuring tape. Tractor wheel slip was calculated as

$$S = \frac{D_1 - D_2}{D_1} \times 100$$

Relationship between soil moisture and wheel slip of tractor at 3 plowing depths, South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

where S = wheel slip

D_1 = distance covered by 10 revolutions of tractor wheel (measured on hard soil without plow attached)

D_2 = distance covered by 10 revolutions of tractor wheel in experimental condition

Wheel slip varied significantly with soil moisture and plowing depth (see figure). Wheel slip was lowest with 15% soil moisture and highest with 25 and 30% soil moisture. At 20-cm plow depth,

wheel slip did not significantly differ at 10, 15, and 20% moisture level.

Wheel slip at plowing depths 10 and 15 cm is less at 15% soil moisture than at 10% because of lower draft resistance. (At 10% moisture, soil was harder than at 15%.)

At 25 and 30% soil moisture, wheel slip tends to increase because of soil resistance as well as the semimuddy condition of the soil. ■

ANNOUNCEMENT

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About 150 senior research leaders and agricultural scientists from developing countries, North America, Australia, and

Europe with interest in systems research, simulation, and modeling are expected to participate.

Papers, posters, and demonstrations will cover genotypic, weather-related, soil, and biological constraints to crop production; farming systems; and training in systems research. For further information, contact Drs. F.W.T. Penning de Vries or P.S. Teng, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, 1099 Manila, Philippines. ■

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